

Monitoring and Analysis of the Development of Social Interaction and Ideology in Different Cultures and the Relationship with the History of Political Thought

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Abstract

The study of political philosophy, a significant academic discipline, focuses on the examination and interpretation of the evolution of diverse forms of governance, societal dynamics, and belief systems across distinct cultural contexts. By analyzing different schools of thought and significant concepts from different time periods, this historical study enhances our comprehension of the political and social organization of civilizations. Postmodern thought is a unique approach that emerged after the modern age and challenges conventional modes of thinking. This article aims to elucidate the Concept of Duality, a fundamental aspect of postmodern philosophy. Furthermore, we will delve into the significance of Friedrich Nietzsche and Sigmund Freud in connection with this idea and their influence on the field of political science.

Keywords: *History Of Political Science, Political Science, Postmodern Thought, Social Interactions, Postmodern Philosophy*

Introduction

The historical transformations that took place in the preceding century had a pivotal role in the emergence and advancement of postmodern concepts and movements. The magnitude of

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intellectual, scientific, political, and social revolution that took place during this time was unparalleled in the recorded history of humanity. Initially, the fundamental assumptions that had been established during the Age of Enlightenment and current scientific advancements were called into question. An instance of this phenomenon is human overconfidence. Humanity gained awareness of its own limits as a consequence of the calamities that transpired throughout this time. It is now able to freely discuss the limits of reason and effectively communicate the discontent produced by representative democracies. During a period when the legitimacy of national governments was being called into question, new types of economic organization that surpassed mass industrial production were developing. Social movements were no longer primarily driven by economic concerns, and smaller groups increasingly focused on formulating globally effective ideas. Each day, a novel international organization was founded with the objective of guaranteeing the enduring conservation of peace. Concurrent with these shifts, there emerged the advancement of postmodern philosophy, which critically examined conventional modes of thinking. This ideology centered on the concept of duality as its primary subject. A core principle of postmodern philosophy is the concept of dichotomy, which posits that conventional thinking relies on binary oppositions and that these oppositions should be critically examined. Postmodern philosophy encompasses an analysis of dichotomies such as "good" and "bad", "right" and "wrong", and "male" and "female". This criticism has had a profound impact on the field of political science.

Aim

Sigmund Freud and Friedrich Nietzsche were very important in the development of the notion of duality, which is regarded as the fundamental principle of postmodern philosophy. Nietzsche's idea of the "Upper Man" challenged conventional moral norms and highlighted humanity's potential to transcend its own limitations. It is important to consider a viewpoint that undermines conventional oppositions in this particular situation. In contrast, Freud undertook thorough investigations into human psychology and provided insights into the workings of people's subconscious minds. This approach focuses on the constraints of

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consciousness and the inherent contradictions inside each person. Various topics within the realm of postmodern thinking are relevant to the field of political science. These include the act of challenging established social norms, altering belief systems, and scrutinizing the distribution of power. The perspectives of Nietzsche and Freud have had a significant influence on the field of political science, particularly in terms of challenging and scrutinizing well-established methodologies. This is attributed to the specific environmental conditions under which they were created. The emergence of postmodern philosophy coincided with the tumultuous events that unfolded throughout the twentieth century. Postmodern philosophy challenged conventional modes of thought. The concept of duality is essential in this particular school of thinking, and the insights provided by philosophers like Nietzsche and Freud played a vital role in fostering a more discerning approach within the realm of political science. The impact of postmodern philosophy on political science is a significant study focus in the postmodern age.

Methodology

The discussion revolves around postmodern ideas and the concept of dualisms. Postmodernism is an intellectual movement that critically examines and questions the underlying ideas of current thinking. Postmodernism is a philosophical movement that questions the commonly accepted concepts of modernity. For instance, in contrast to the modern period's focus on concepts like universality and objectivity, postmodernism challenges these notions and welcomes a higher level of subjectivity and a wider range of opinions.

Literature Review

The fundamental tenet of postmodernism is that humans possess the capacity to see and construe reality from many perspectives. Postmodern philosophy is based on these principles, and it challenges commonly accepted interpretations of current thinking with its revolutionary

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impact.

During the period known as modernity, there is a strong emphasis on concepts such as enlightenment, the advancement of the scientific method, progress, and universality. This era spans from the 18th century until the present day. Postmodernism challenges the ideals promoted by modernity. Postmodernity is an era marked by the interrogation of established concepts and the cultivation of a mindset that is both more liberated and analytical. This ideology highlights the breakdown of the norms established during the modern era and the rise of different viewpoints in the postmodern era. Duality is seen as a basic notion in postmodern thinking. Postmodernism is an intellectual movement that contends that conventional thinking relies on binary oppositions and suggests that these oppositions should be critically examined. Postmodern philosophy criticizes dichotomies such as "good" and "bad", "right" and "wrong", and "male" and "female". This concept seeks to acknowledge the presence of many viewpoints and to transcend conflicts. Postmodernism plays a significant role in the realm of political science, including a broad array of topics such as the analysis of power relations, the interrogation of societal norms, and the alteration of paradigms. The objective of postmodernism is to thoroughly analyze social and political matters while simultaneously scrutinizing conventional approaches used in the field of political science. The fundamental principle of postmodernism is on the notion of shifting ideologies. Conventional ideologies are being substituted by more adaptable and varied forms of thinking, and postmodern philosophy examines the effects of ideologies on human behavior and societal organization. Postmodernism challenges established social norms and values. Postmodernism has influenced several academic disciplines, prompting them to challenge the commonly accepted ethical and societal norms. A crucial element of postmodern philosophy is the recognition that social norms are subjective.

The political arena is a domain that is impacted by postmodern concepts. It acknowledges the presence of many viewpoints while also scrutinizing power relations and political conflicts. A more rigorous examination of democratic processes may be achieved by scrutinizing the dichotomies present in politics.

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Postmodernism explores the essence of power and the dynamics between different sources of power. The notion of postmodernism presents concerns about the establishment, preservation, and validation of authority. A crucial element of social revolution is the critical examination of authority. A significant critique of postmodern philosophy is on the presence of gender binary classifications. Challenging gender roles and conventions is a core concept of postmodern art practice. It asserts that gender binary classifications are subjective and subject to potential future changes.

Argument

Analysis of the Importance of Sigmund Freud and Friedrich Nietzsche

Both Sigmund Freud and Friedrich Nietzsche are influential intellectuals of the twentieth century who have made substantial contributions to the advancement of postmodern ideology. Both individuals have shown the ability to question conventional modes of thought and provide fresh viewpoints via their original contributions in their respective fields. The significance and impact of these thinkers is evident in their contributions to the core concepts of postmodernism, such as the interrogation of values and the diversity of identities.

Friedrich Nietzsche is widely acknowledged as the pioneer who initiated a substantial transformation in the approach to philosophy and moral thinking. One of the core tenets of postmodernism is the critical examination of values, and his ideas have a substantial impact on this artistic and intellectual movement. Nietzsche challenged the concept of "slave morality" and interrogated the conventional moral principles embraced by society. "Beyond Good and Evil" is a literary work in which Nietzsche delves into the origins of societal moral standards and contends that these ideals do not stem from inherent human nature. He believes that conventional moral norms directly contradict man's quest for power and restrict his potential. Nietzsche's books prominently feature the notion of the "Superior Man," highlighting the need of individuals breaking free from conventional standards and constructing their own ideals. The emergence of the notion of "multiplicity of values" is regarded as an important concept in

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postmodern philosophy. Nietzsche's ideas established the intellectual underpinnings of the postmodern era and promoted the scrutiny of conventional moral power. Nietzsche's works had a vital role in establishing this groundwork.

Sigmund Freud is largely regarded as the trailblazer of psychoanalysis, and his groundbreaking contributions to the area of human psychology are highly acknowledged. Freud's contributions to our knowledge of the unconscious and the inner world of humans have greatly influenced the development of postmodern philosophy. Freud posited that the majority of human behavior and ideas stem from the unconscious mind of a person. An individual's formation of identity is shaped by their unconscious motivations and internal struggles. Freud's psychoanalytic views prompted us to delve into several subjects such as gender binaries, sexual identity, and the formation of identities. Consequently, this gave rise to the postmodern movement of thinking which prioritizes the interrogation of many identities and social norms. The ideas of Nietzsche and Freud had a crucial role in establishing two essential principles of postmodern thought: the recognition of many identities and the acknowledgment of diverse sets of values. Nietzsche had a pessimistic perspective towards established moral principles and highlighted the autonomy of individuals in determining their own moral values. This had a significant role in shaping postmodernism's understanding of the subjective and diverse nature of values. Freud delved into the depths of the unconscious mind, while also establishing a structure for the formation of personal identities and the questioning of societal norms about gender. Freud's psychoanalytic approach contributed to the further development of this viewpoint, while postmodern philosophy advocated for the diversity of identities and the subjective nature of social norms.

Friedrich Nietzsche, the third The occurrence happened on October 15, 1844, in Rocken, Germany. Nietzsche was exposed to religious ideas throughout his formative years due to his father's position as a Lutheran minister of grace. At the beginning of his academic journey, he enrolled at the University of Leipzig, focusing his studies on philology and theology. Subsequently, his fascination with philology intensified, prompting him to direct his concentration towards the study of ancient literature and languages. The works of Nietzsche, including Thus Spoke Zarathustra, The Genealogy of Morality, and Beyond Good and Evil,

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have had a profound impact on current philosophy, serving as its fundamental basis. From a critical standpoint, he used these works to examine ethical principles, societal norms, and the fundamental nature of humanity. Nietzsche's writings have had a substantial impact on the development of postmodern philosophy.

Despite the intricate nature of Nietzsche's philosophical framework, it does include a few fundamental ideas. One concept that is often discussed is the notion of the "Death of God." Nietzsche contends that the prevailing framework of modern thinking has undergone a fundamental shift due to the skepticism around the existence of God. He contends that because to the demise of God, humans no longer possess a universally recognized moral authority and are hence accountable for establishing their own moral principles.

The second essential element of his philosophy is based on the notion of the "Übermensch" (sometimes referred to as the "New Man"). Nietzsche posits that people possess the capacity to diverge from societal conventions and establish their own system of principles. This is a rejection of established conventional moral norms and places importance on the personal growth and fulfillment of an individual. Nietzsche also made substantial contributions to the realm of political ideas. His critical perspective challenges the legitimacy of different political structures including conventional ones. Nietzsche examines the tension between "slave morality" and "master morality" and analyzes its impact on political philosophy. Nietzsche emphasizes the subjective character of values. He asserts that each individual have the capacity to cultivate their own set of principles, which need to be based on their own life experiences. The notion of "plurality of values" is a fundamental idea in postmodernism, and it serves as the predecessor to this principle. Furthermore, Nietzsche underscores the paramount significance of personal autonomy. The capacity of individuals to diverge from conventional norms and engage in distinctive thinking is enhanced when they are given the autonomy to autonomously cultivate their own personal principles. This phenomenon gives birth to postmodern concepts and fosters the aspirations of individuals who want personal autonomy. Friedrich Nietzsche's life and works have had a profound influence on all facets of modern thinking. His core ideas, which sparked intellectual revolutions in the subjectivity of values and the emphasis on personal liberty, have made substantial contributions to the realms of postmodern thinking and political

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theory, as well as to the area of political philosophy. Undoubtedly, Nietzsche's views have had a vital role in shaping the essential principles that underpin the postmodern age. Nietzsche's thoughts have had a significant impact on the advancement of postmodern philosophy and social critique (Arnhart, 2005: 442). From his point of view, traditional moral divisions have been challenged, a new and distinctive viewpoint has been presented, and existing divisions have been eradicated, while the importance of personal values has been highlighted. Nietzsche explores the conflict between slave morality and master morality in his works, examining how individuals form value judgments and societal standards (Arnhart, 2005: 445-46). These texts represent a component of Nietzsche's intellectual inheritance. In addition, he highlights the process by which people form their own systems of beliefs, using the concept of the will to power (Arnhart, 2005: 435). Nietzsche's views have been a significant influence on philosophical movements that prioritize human freedom and postmodern philosophy. Furthermore, Nietzsche's concepts provide a viewpoint that challenges moral divisions (Nietzsche, 2011: 1500-1501). Nietzsche's theories have a significant place in the realm of postmodern philosophy.

Sigmund Freud is widely regarded as one of the most influential psychologists of the 19th and 20th centuries, as stated by Craib (2001: 31). Nevertheless, he is usually acknowledged as the pioneer of psychoanalysis. Furthermore, he achieved notable breakthroughs in understanding human behavior and the cognitive processes that take place in the mind. The paragraph provides a more detailed discussion of Freud's life, psychoanalytic theory, and contributions to political philosophy (Freud, 2011: 1545-1546). Sigmund Freud, born on May 6, 1856, died on September 23, 1939. He was born and grew up in Vienna, Austria. Upon finishing his medical school, he started his research on the nervous system and conducted detailed observations, particularly in relation to the management of patients suffering from hysteria (Craib, 2001: 31). The collaborative work "Treatise on Hysteria" was authored by Sigmund Freud and Josef Breuer and released in the year 1895. This study was significant in establishing the groundwork for the concept of psychoanalysis and positing that neuroses were attributed to sexual encounters. Sigmund Freud originated the concept of psychoanalysis as a means to comprehend the hidden influences that drive human behavior and mental functions.

Unconscious

Freud posited the existence of an unconscious element of the human mind, which he felt had profound implications that extended beyond conscious awareness. The impact of this subconscious on human behavior, thoughts, and emotions is substantial. Freud posited that dreams are a reflection of hidden desires and thoughts that exist in the unconscious mind. Consequently, the study and interpretation of dreams play a crucial role in the field of psychoanalysis (Freud, 2011: 1545-1546). "Psychoanalysis and Dreams" Freud made a significant contribution by examining the hidden variables that shape human conduct and societal conventions. Freud undertook this study with the intention of questioning and challenging established social conventions. Consequently, there was a rise in the level of public attention regarding the critique and alteration of societal frameworks (Tannenbaum and Schultz, 2005: 365). Analyzing and comparing sexuality and gender roles. Freud conducted research on the impact of sexuality on human behavior and societal norms. Furthermore, he emphasized the significant role that unconscious processes play in shaping sexual identity and gender roles (Tannenbaum and Schultz, 2005: 362).

Freud's views had a significant role in initiating an era referred to as the "age of doubt" throughout the latter part of the 20th century. Tannenbaum and Schultz (2005: 365) assert that his work had a substantial influence on the domains of psychology, philosophy, and the social sciences. It offered a fresh viewpoint for comprehending the intricacies and subconscious influences driving human behavior. Freud's core concepts remain very significant in endeavors to delve into the intricacies of the human psyche and comprehend the workings of the subconscious. Furthermore, they provide a solid foundation for the evaluation and examination of societal and cultural standards and patterns of conduct (Craib, 2001: 60). Freud posited that the pleasure principle serves as the primary motivator for human life. This concept has a substantial influence on our cognitive faculties. However, our pursuit of pleasure is impeded by three factors: the limitations of the human body, the external surroundings, and our relationships with other individuals. The ego and superego are responsible for suppressing the id, which is

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essential for achieving effective collaboration with others. Nevertheless, to inhibit the id, individuals construct very intricate defensive mechanisms. Due to this circumstance, individuals are compelled to engage in an ongoing battle with both their own selves and the surrounding world (Tannenbaum and Schultz, 2005: 362).

In his book titled "The Ego and the Id and the Complete Introductory Lectures on Psychoanalysis", Freud explores the concepts of the human psyche and consciousness. According to Freud, the human mind and awareness are comprised of three phases. The id, ego, and superego are three psychological constructs that develop as a consequence of the conflict with parental figures throughout early childhood. The id, often referred to as the lower self, represents fundamental human impulses and urges, including love and sexuality. Our personality's energy reservoir propels our internal energy outward and anticipates rapid fulfillment (Craib, 2001: 57).

The id, our most primal aspect, serves as the source of energy from which our personality originates. Nevertheless, people are susceptible to both internal and external forces, and the ego, also referred to as the self, is the only entity capable of maintaining equilibrium between these two levels of demands. In this particular context, the ego symbolizes the rational aspect of human nature. Conversely, the ego has an innate mechanism of unconscious protection that regulates the impulses of the id. Thus, people have the capacity to cultivate a sense of self-importance by altering their connection with the external environment (Craib, 2001: 60).

The superego, also known as the higher self, is a sort of conscience regulation that we internalize to assist the ego in maintaining control over the id. The superego is directly linked to our conscious experiences, including self-evaluation, self-imposed norms, and self-criticism for deviating from expected behavior. Craib (2001: 60) argues that the superego is manifested in daily life via entities like family, religion, and government. Freud posited that the pleasure principle serves as the primary motivator for human life. This concept has a substantial influence on our cognitive faculties. However, our pursuit of pleasure is impeded by three factors: the limitations of the human body, the external surroundings, and our relationships with other individuals. The ego and superego play a crucial role in repressing the id, which is

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essential for achieving effective collaboration with others. Nevertheless, individuals create very intricate defensive mechanisms to repress their subconscious desires. Consequently, individuals are compelled to engage in an ongoing battle with their own selves and the surrounding environment (Tannenbaum and Schultz, 2005: 362).

Freud posits that our civilization is constructed as a means of safeguarding ourselves from nature and regulating our social relationships. However, the downside of civilization is that it compels us to endure perpetual conflict and unhappiness. Freud believes that those residing in primitive communities are likely to have more happiness compared to those living in civilized ones. Individuals living in primitive civilizations may exhibit heightened sensitivity towards the impacts of nature, although they are also required to exert less restraint over their desires (Tannenbaum and Schultz, 2005: 363-364). To safeguard the cultural life that people have created, the state must establish institutional institutions that are both restricting and regulating. According to Tannenbaum and Schultz (2005: 364), humans can only live together and be part of civilization when the rules of politics exert influence on human behavior. This is essential for individuals to become citizens of civilization. According to Freud, Eros, the goddess of love, is the dominant force responsible for preserving the stability of these social structures (Tannenbaum and Schultz, 2005: 365). Love, sexual desire, or the "life force" is the predominant and influential factor at play in this process. Given these circumstances, love, sexuality, and the need for self-preservation serve as the primary catalysts for the development of civilization. Freud does not consider reason to be the primary driving factor in the creation of civilization. According to Freud, people must relinquish some desires in order to enjoy the advantages of living in a society. This concept is comparable to the idea of a social compact proposed by Locke (Tannenbaum and Schultz, 2005: 365). Freud's thesis has been likened to the Lockean social compact. Freud believes that political life exhibits a hierarchical competitive framework, which is observable and comprehensible. This conflict impacts the realms of the individual, family, and society. Regarding this specific matter, the example provided by Freud concerning the Oedipus complex is quite intriguing. Oedipus, a character from Greek mythology, unwittingly enters into a marriage with his own mother and bears the guilt of causing his father's demise. Freud posited that the father in this tale symbolizes power, while

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the kid (Oedipus) symbolizes incestuous desires, and the act of murdering the father symbolizes the development of the superego. According to him, during the "phallic period" that takes place between the ages of three and four, the young individual is said to have sexual attraction towards their mother. Alternatively, he may suppress his affection for his mother due to a fear of being emasculated by his father. Additionally, he acknowledges his father as a symbol of power. Freud posits that the majority of psychological tensions that stem from family life are mirrored in social life and are regarded as forbidden (Craib, 2001: 82-92). In addition to this, there are several more issues that pose a danger to social life. Furthermore, the presence of the "death instinct" linked to the deity of war, Thanatos, acts as a directing influence for individuals. The "death instinct" functions as a counteracting force to Eros. Conversely, Thanatos is accountable for uniting individuals, whilst Eros is accountable for uniting them. Freud's notion of the death instinct was not just drawn from his therapeutic experiences, but also influenced by his exploration of political life in Europe before World War II (Craib, 2001: 37). Freud's perspectives emerged from his quest to comprehend political existence. During the course of civilization, the illogical and subconscious aspects of human psychology are apprehended and subjected to the influence of societal regulations. Nevertheless, as a consequence, people engage in a continuous struggle with both their own selves and the larger community. Due to this tension, an illogical sense of release is activated, causing individuals to live with the perception that they are constantly causing harm to themselves.

The significance of Freud's beliefs and his profound impact on the disciplines of psychology and social sciences are underscored by providing details about Freud's history and his psychoanalytic theory. Freud's endeavors to comprehend the intricacies and subconscious elements influencing human conduct have had a noteworthy impact on the advancement of modern psychology and the challenging of societal norms. Freud's perspectives had a substantial influence on the fields of psychology, philosophy, and the social sciences. Additionally, they made substantial contributions to the emergence of the "Age of Skepticism" throughout the latter part of the 20th century. Sigmund Freud's life and ideas substantially facilitated efforts to comprehend the human psyche and challenge societal conventions, establishing him as a renowned figure in the discipline. Freud's psychoanalytic theory has

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proven to be an excellent tool for finding and comprehending the unconscious variables that impact human behavior. Freud's political ideas during this period fueled a heightened curiosity in the analysis and improvement of social structures. This was accomplished via an examination of the fundamental conflicts that form the basis of civilization and societal norms. Freud's views have a lasting impact on the field of human psychology and the understanding of social dynamics.

Ten Final Thoughts

The political ideology of Europe throughout the 19th and early 20th centuries was profoundly shaped by the ideas of Nietzsche and Freud, which gained significant popularity in Europe during that time period. In contrast to Freud's focus on human behavior and subconscious forces, Nietzsche is renowned for his exploration of nihilism and his prophetic insights into the future. Freud's thinking was shaped by the somber atmosphere that prevailed throughout the interwar period. After Nietzsche's death, his warnings materialized as Europe was engulfed in a devastating catastrophe. Conversely, Nietzsche anticipated the emergence of a novel "human" in the future.

Conclusion

Contrarily, Freud postulated that the perpetual clash between human instincts and societal norms would generate ongoing tension, resulting in remnants of his despondency. The influence of Freud continues to thrive in the continual endeavor to explore our subconscious mind. Consequently, this has compelled us to endeavor to comprehend the profound and intricate aspects of the human psyche. The issues highlighted by these two eminent thinkers remain pertinent even in contemporary society. Writers that adopt the postmodern style carry on the legacy of Nietzsche and Freud by extending its boundaries. Conversely, contemporary individuals prioritize the exploration of novel methodologies to guarantee the ongoing existence

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of human society. Currently, critical and multi-perspective thinking is progressively supplanting positivist thought as the prevailing mode of thought in contemporary society. Freud and Nietzsche are both regarded as significant figures in the field of political science. Nietzsche's exploration of nihilism and human values offered a thorough analysis of the core issues in political philosophy. Freud's criticisms of human conduct and societal norms had a significant impact on political philosophy, prompting a reevaluation of cultural institutions and social standards. These philosophers made notable contributions to the area of political science by endeavoring to comprehend the intricacies of human nature and the subconscious factors that influence them. In the context of this debate, the ideas put forward by Nietzsche and Freud have greatly influenced the advancement of political science and social reasoning.

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